

Absorption Spectra of Some Substituted Chalcones*—III

DURGA NATH DHAR† & R. K. SINGH

Department of Chemistry, Indian Institute of Technology, Kanpur (India)

Manuscript received 15 October 1971; accepted for publication 9 February 1972

The electronic spectra of fourteen fluorochalcones have been studied. Some possible reasons for the observed spectral shifts with substitution are discussed.

The ultraviolet spectra of chalcones have been studied by various groups of investigators¹⁻⁵. These studies have led to some interesting generalizations in respect of ultraviolet absorption as a function of substitution in chalcone system. With a view to furthering our understanding into the subject we have examined the ultraviolet and near-visible spectra of 4'-fluorochalcones and the corresponding chalcone analogues containing a polynuclear or heteroaromatic ring system.

The following chalcones were prepared and examined :

R = unsubstituted/substituted phenyl group (Ring A) (Cf. Table 1, Compd. 2-11).

R = 1-Naphthyl and 9-anthracyl group (Cf. Compd. 12 and 13).

R = 2-Pyrrolyl and 2-furyl group (Cf. Compd. 14 and 15).

EXPERIMENTAL AND RESULTS

The chalcones required for the present study were prepared by the Claisen-Schmidt condensation of 4-fluoroacetophenone with aromatic, hetero-aromatic and polynuclear-aromatic aldehydes and were crystallised several times before use. Their preparation and physical properties are reported elsewhere².

The ultraviolet and near visible spectra were recorded, in 95% ethanol, on the Beckman DB spectrophotometer using 1.0 cm cell. The concentration of the alcoholic solution ranged from 0.94×10^{-5} to 8.85×10^{-5} mole/litre. The values of λ_{max} and ϵ for the various chalcones are summarised in table 1.

* Taken in part from M.Sc. thesis of R. K. Singh submitted to the Department of Chemistry, Indian Institute of Technology, Kanpur (1968).

† To whom all enquiries should be addressed.

TABLE I

Electronic Absorption of Substituted Chalcones in Ethanolic solution

Compd. No.	Substituents		Band II		Band I	
	Ring A	Ring B	λ_{max} (ϵ)		(K-Band) λ_{max} (ϵ)	
1.	—	—	226 ⁵ (10,500)	—	310 (27,000)	—
2.	—	4'-F	226 (9,630)	0	313 (25,200)	+3
3.	2-Cl	4'-F	232 (9,330)	+6	306 (21,100)	-7
4.	4-Cl	4'-F	229 (13,100)	+3	316 (29,000)	+3
5.	3-NO ₂	4'-F	— —		294 (24,000)	-19
6.	4-N(CH ₃) ₂	4'-F	268 (58,700)	+42	425 (13,000)	+112
					330 (3,300)	
7.	2,3-(OCH ₃) ₂	4'-F	250 (8,000)	+24	316 (23,000)	+3
8.	3,4-(OCH ₃) ₂	4'-F	264 (12,100)	+38	359 (17,300)	+46
9.	3-OH,4-OCH ₃	4'-F	264 (14,200)	+38	366 (17,700)	+53
10.	5-Br, 2,4(OCH ₃) ₂	4'-F	264 (54,100)	+38	468 (11,300)	+155
					364 (64,700)	
11.	6-Br, 2,4(OCH ₃) ₂	4'-F	266 (13,200)	+40	365 (12,500)	+52
					314 (10,200)	
12.	1-naphthyl	4'-F	267 (19,100)	+41	358 (14,400)	+45
13.	9-Anthracyl	4'-F	253 (12,900)	+27	414 (77,000)	+101
14.	2-Pyrrolyl	4'-F	246 (9,300)	+20	390 (24,800)	+77
15.	2-Furyl	4'-F	262 (15,400)	+36	345 (51,200)	+32
			226 (26,000)			
			220 (43,400)			

DISCUSSION

The examination of table 1 shows that all these chalcones show two main regions of absorption: One in the range of 294–468 $m\mu$ (referred to as Band I or K-band) arising, probably, due to $\pi-\pi^*$ electronic transition of the whole molecule; while the other absorption lies in the range of 226–268 $m\mu$ (band II). The intensity of the latter band is usually weaker than the intensity of the K-band (exceptions, compounds 6, 10, 11 and 12). This conclusion is in agreement with the generalization advanced by Jurd and Horowitz³. Substitution in ring A of chalcone molecule, causes invariably a red-shift of band-II (cf. compound 2-11), while the shift in band-I seems to be dependent upon the nature and the position of the substituent(s). Thus, 2-chloro or 3-nitro substituents (ring A) cause hypsochromic

effects (cf. compound 3 and 5); while 4-chloro-, 4-dimethylamino-, 2,3 (and 3,4-)dimethoxy-, 3-hydroxy-4-methoxy- and 5- (and 6-) bromo-2,4-dimethoxy substituents cause bathochromic shifts (cf. compds. 4, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11). Substitution, in ring B, of para fluoro group, however causes a small bathochromic shift ($\Delta\lambda$, $+3m\mu$) in comparison to the unsubstituted chalcone (cf. compounds 1 and 2).

Substitution by a chloro group in the ortho position (ring A) produces a hypsochromic effect ($\Delta\lambda$, $-7m\mu$) accompanied with reduction in absorptivity. The hypsochromic effect is also observed in the case of 2-chlorochalcone studied by Wheeler *et al.*⁵ who attribute this effect to be due to a steric factor. This results in the deformation of ring A from the plane of the chalcone molecule. The angle of deformation in such situation, is calculable if one assumes that there is no deformation in case of *p*-isomer. Thus

$$\cos^2 \theta = \frac{\epsilon_a}{\epsilon_o}$$

ϵ_a = Extinction Coefficient for the ortho substituted chalcone, and

ϵ_o = Extinction Coefficient for the para substituted chalcone.

The calculated angle of deformation for 2-chloro-4'-fluorochalcone turns out to be 35°. The value reported by Wheeler *et al.*⁵ for 2-chlorochalcone is 36°.

O-Substitution by a methoxyl group (ring A) has, however, been observed to produce a bathochromic shift (cf. compds. 7, 10 and 11). The 2-methoxy group apparently has an inherent tendency to produce a bathochromic effect⁶ which is also substantiated by the work of Noyce & Jorgenson⁷. ($\Delta\lambda = +38m\mu$ for 2-Methoxychalcone compared to the unsubstituted compound). Contrary to the large bathochromic shift as observed in 2-methoxy 4'-fluorochalcone, 2,3-dimethoxy-4'-fluorochalcone shows only a small bathochromic shift ($\Delta\lambda = +3m\mu$). This could be explained on the basis of "buttressing effect", the influence wherein the steric effect of 2-methoxy substituent becomes more important because of the close proximity of another methoxy substituent. The 2,4-dimethoxy-5-bromo-4'-fluorochalcone (cf. compound 10) shows a large bathochromic shift ($\Delta\lambda$, $+155m\mu$). The two methoxyl substituents in this case are causing enhancement of their respective bathochromic effects. In the case of 2,4-dimethoxy-6-bromo-4'-fluorochalcone, however, there is a large decrease in the absorptivity compared to compound 10. This effect is understandable on the ground of steric interactions caused by the two ortho substituents, viz., 2-methoxy and 6-bromo substituents, which forces the ring A out of plane of the chalcone molecule. The large bathochromic shifts exhibited by 3,4-dimethoxy-4'-fluoro chalcone and 3-hydroxy-4-methoxy-4'-fluorochalcone (cf. compounds 8 and 9) are due to methoxyl function acting by resonance. In the case of 4-chloro-4'-fluorochalcone the small red shift ($\Delta\lambda$, $+3m\mu$) arises because the resonance effect dominates over the inductive effect.

The unusually large bathochromic shift ($\Delta\lambda$, +112 m μ), observed in the case of 4-dimethylamino-4'-fluoro-chalcone (cf. compound 6) is explicable on the grounds of extended conjugation due to the availability of lone pair electrons on the nitrogen and also due to the positive inductive effect of the two methyl groups attached to the nitrogen atom.

Introduction of a meta-nitro substituent (cf. compound 5) produces a hypsochromic effect ($\Delta\lambda$, -19 m μ) accompanied with diminution in the intensity of absorption ($\sim 40\%$). This result is in agreement with our earlier observations⁶ as well as with those reported by Szamant and Basso⁴.

In the case of chalcones, containing mononuclear aromatic ring system, described above, the shift in the K-band seems to be intimately linked up with the extent of mobility of the lone pair electrons (ring A substitution in ortho and/or para position), and also on the inductive and the steric effects. Thus the bathochromic shift caused by the different substituents follows the order :

In the case of chalcone analogues, containing polynuclear aromatic ring system (cf. compounds 12 and 13) the red shifts observed are due to extended conjugation. In the case of heteroaromatic chalcone analogues (cf. compds. 14 and 15) the bathochromic shift seems to be dependent upon the ease of delocalisation of the lone pair electrons on the heteroatom of ring A. Thus :

The trend in the bathochromic shift of compounds 12-15 are as follows :

REFERENCES

1. D. N. Dhar and D. V. Singhal, *Spectrochim. Acta.*, 1970, **26**(A), 1171.
2. D. N. Dhar and R. K. Singh, *Zhur. obschei. Khim.*, 1970, **40**(5), 1156.
3. L. Jurd and R. M. Horowitz, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1961, **26**, 2561.
4. H. H. Szamant and A. J. Basso, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, **74**, 4397.
5. O. H. Wheeler, P. H. Gore, M. Santiago and R. Baez., *Canad. J. Chem.*, 1964, **42**, 2580.
6. D. N. Dhar and R. K. Singh, unpublished results.
7. D. S. Noyce and M. J. Jorgenson, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, **84**, 4312.